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SYNTHESIS OF CARTHAMINE DERIVATIVES

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Annotation: Compounds synthesized on the basis of cartamic acid and its derivatives are substances with high biological activity, and many preparations and dyes have been obtained on the basis of these compounds. Aromatic alcohols, phthalimide and its derivatives, galagen-containing radicals were mainly used in the synthesis of carthamic acid and its derivatives.

Key words: HSYA- Hyrdoxysaflor A, CY-yellow cartamine, SYA-Saflor A, SY-safflower yellow, HSYB-Hydroxyflor B, HSYC-Hydroxyflor C, DPPH-extract has high reducing power and antioxidant activity

Introduction In recent years, the production of synthetic chemical dyes in food and cosmetics has been growing rapidly[1]. Asparagus (*Carthamus tinctorius* L.), an annual herb of the Asteraceae family, is an important industrial crop whose petals contain Cglucosylquinochalcone flavonoids, which give yellow and red pigments [2]. These colorants are used as coloring agents in processed food, soft drinks, cosmetics, textile industry and medicine. Pigments have some medicinal properties such as

cardiovascular diseases, rheumatism, diabetes [3], high blood pressure [4] and they have shown antioxidant and hepatoprotective activity [5].

Infusions and tinctures based on safflower help to get rid of swelling. By using safflower, you can improve blood circulation in the body. The plant has the ability to thin the blood, which is a treatment for heart attacks and strokes. Chemical composition of green parts and flowers of safflower The aerial parts are high in carbon (42.7–49.1% daily weight) and relatively low in nitrogen (0.36–1.23%) [6]. They contain carthamusin A [7], β -daucosterol and stigmasterol [8]. The chemical composition of flowers is interesting and rich, more than 200 substances have been identified so far [11]. Flower petals contain 1.82% protein, 4.8% lipids, 11.6% crude fiber, 10.8% ash, and their moisture content is 4.7% [9]. They also contain alkaloids, flavonoids, lignanoids, organic acids and polyacetylenes [11, 10], alkanediols, riboflavin, steroids and quinochalcone C glycosides. Carthamucin A $C_{24}H_{28}O_8$ white crystal [8]

1. Carthamic acid and chloromethylphthalimide reaction.

The above reaction is carried out due to the phenol group contained in cartamine.

Characteristic absorption areas of cartamine methylphthalimide ester (cm⁻¹): deformation vibrations of the CH bond in the 1,2-disubstituted aromatic ring at 737 cm⁻¹; 1454 cm⁻¹ valence vibrations of C=C bonds in the aromatic ring and 2954 cm⁻¹, 3066 cm⁻¹ C-H bonds, 1718 cm⁻¹, 3437 cm⁻¹ -CO-NH- amide; CH₂ group asymmetric at 2961 cm⁻¹, symmetric valence vibrations at 2932 cm⁻¹; valence vibrations of CH₂ group attached to nitrogen at 1454 cm⁻¹; 1727 cm⁻¹.

Reaction of butyl bromide with carthamic acid

It shows the reaction of cartamine with butyl bromide. This reaction also occurs with the phenolic group in cartamine.

According to the results of the analysis: in the absorption areas of 2947, 3099 cm^{-1} , low intensity absorption lines corresponding to the $=\text{C-H}$ bonds in the aromatic ring of the substance can be seen. In the region of 2606 cm^{-1} , there are symmetric valence vibrations belonging to the $-\text{CH}_2$ group, 1082 cm^{-1} to the $-\text{C}(\text{O})-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2$ bond, in the absorption region of 1723 cm^{-1} there is an intense vibration belonging to the $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group valence vibrations, and in absorption areas such as 750 cm^{-1} (benzene ring)- CH , 1615, 1706, 1529 cm^{-1} , a ring vibration belonging to an aromatic ring of medium intensity can be observed. In the region of 2749, 3099 cm^{-1} , valence vibrations related to hydrocarbon groups were observed.

3. Reaction of carthamic acid sodium salt and benzyl alcohol.

As a result of this reaction, benzyl ester of cartamine is formed. Below is the IK spectrum of the resulting substance.

(3)

According to the results of the analysis: in the absorption areas of 2929, 3058 cm^{-1} , one can see low intensity absorption lines related to $=\text{C}-\text{H}$ bonds in the aromatic ring of the substance. In the 2749 cm^{-1} region, there are symmetric valence vibrations belonging to the $-\text{CH}_2$ group, 1055 cm^{-1} to the $-\text{C}(\text{O})-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2$ bond, and in the 1723 cm^{-1} absorption region, there is an intense vibration belonging to the $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group valence vibrations, and in absorption areas such as 720 cm^{-1} (benzene ring)- CH , 1656, 1501, 1597 cm^{-1} , a ring vibration belonging to an aromatic ring of medium intensity

can be observed. In the 2749, 3058 cm⁻¹ area, valence vibrations related to hydrocarbon groups were observed.

As a conclusion, we can say that by analyzing the results of the reaction, the compounds formed with cartamine are widely used in various fields. The biological activity of the produced substances was also studied. The reaction of carthamine with chloromethylolphthalimide was carried out in the presence of pyridine, and it was determined that carthamine methylolphthalimide was formed.

The reaction of carthamic acid and butyl bromide was studied. Our product obtained as a result of the reaction was found to be used as a natural dye.

The synthesis of cartamic acid and its derivatives was studied and the use of these substances in chemical technology, food industry and pharmaceuticals was studied.

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